

THE USAGE OF MODERN TEST SYSTEMS WHILE TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF MEDICAL CHEMISTRY

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It is important to improve the knowledge, skills and abilities of students in the field of medicinal chemistry and to control the process. Correctly organized theoretical questions allow the use of various tools to deepen the acquired knowledge and, most importantly, to develop their personal skills. Controlling the formation of knowledge and skills in the educational process takes an important place. In particular, control has the following functions:

Diagnostic function of control. As a result of control, the level of knowledge and skill formation is determined.

The function of supervision is to increase students' enthusiasm for learning. This involves the correct evaluation of the knowledge and skills acquired as a result of various incentives or supervision.

Educational function. Educational function of control and evaluation function of control. The use of test programs is effective in monitoring students' knowledge. There are several programs that allow teachers to create tests. Among these programs, the one with a convenient interface is the iSpring program.

What is iSpring Learn?

iSpring Learn is a cloud-based LMS for online corporate training that allows you to learn quickly. The LMS has an intuitive interface that makes it easy-to-use for both learners and training managers. iSpring Learn provides users with all essential LMS features plus additional components at a fair price. Whatever pricing plan users have, they always get a full package of LMS features and ongoing updates. To organize online learning, you just need to sign up for iSpring Learn, upload

your training materials, and assign training. Training content can be created from existing materials or it can be easily built with iSpring's authoring toolkit.

Overview of iSpring Learn benefits

With iSpring Learn, you can generate a variety of training results quickly:

1. Onboarding. With iSpring Learn, employees can enter the workflow faster. Introduce your learners to products, operations, and corporate culture.

2. Product training. Employees can access iSpring Learn on their desktops, tablets, or mobile devices any time they need to get the latest product information and updates on work practices quickly.

3. Sales training. You can teach your agents the best sales techniques, measure their product knowledge, and train communication techniques in a safe-to-fail environment and watch their productivity grow.

4. Channel training. iSpring Learn allows you to develop a unified knowledge base for your representatives and partners and keep everyone aware of corporate standards.

5. Compliance training. Make compliance training more effective by putting it online. Deliver and update content on your learning portal to ensure employee compliance.

6. Certification. With iSpring Learn, you can evaluate your employees' progress with online tests, interactions, and self-assessments. iSpring Learn automatically generates reports so you can see the big picture.

7. 360-Degree performance appraisal. 360-Degree assessment helps to identify the employee's strengths, areas of improvement, and how well they are suited for their roles.

The iSpring program allows you to create eleven different types of tests. Among them, one of the ones that increases the student's interest is the "True/false" test type. In this way, the student increases the level of speed and intelligence in answering tests. One of the widely used software for creating electronic information educational resources is the iSpring program. Usually, Microsoft

Power Point software is used in the process of preparing a presentation. But such presentations can only be in the format of this product (ppt, pptx). Currently, due to the development of Internet technologies and, in turn, the emergence of distance education, presentation files are in flash (swf) format for viewing directly online in the Internet browser itself. or must be a file created on the basis of HTML 5 technology. By now, programs have been created that allow creating a flash-roll from a presentation prepared in PowerPoint. The product is called iSpring and has options like iSpring QuizMarker, iSpring PRO, and iSpring Kinetics.

According to independent experts, this product is one of the best today in terms of speed, quality of conversion from one format to another, and number of options. iSpring not only you to create flash-presentations, but also allows you to create videos that can be used in the educational process, and in particular, they can be interactively connected, including various forms of surveys and electronic tests. iSpring Suite is a professional tool for creating e-learning courses in PowerPoint. Using the iSpring program, the user can create and publish educational courses in several stages:

- a) create educational courses based on Power Point presentations;
- b) Combine audio and video files;
- c) Create interactive tests;
- d) Creating interactive blocks;
- e) Preparation of information for the distance education system.

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